

Mergers and acquisitions in the public research sector. Towards a comprehensive typology

Barbara Heller-Schuh¹, Benedetto Lepori², Martina Neuländtner¹

¹Center for Innovation Systems & Policy, AIT Austrian Institute of Technology, 1210 Vienna, Austria.

²Faculty of Communication Sciences, Università della Svizzera italiana, 6904 Lugano, Switzerland.

This article has been accepted for publication in Research Evaluation published by Oxford University Press.

Abstract

While the literature on firm mergers and acquisitions (M&A) is quite extensive, systematic approaches to analyse mergers in the public research sector are still scarce and focus only on the higher education sector. This paper provides, for the first time, systematic empirical evidence on the extent and characteristics of M&A in public-sector research in Europe, by building on a novel dataset comprising demographic events since the year 2000. The goal of this study is to characterize such events in terms of organizations involved, types of events and regional distribution.

We find that M&A constituted a major change process within European public research. Nearly 400 events occurred in Europe between 2000 and 2016 with an increasing trend over time; M&A involved nearly one-fifth of public-sector research organizations and were geographically distributed across two-fifths of all European regions. Demographic events concerned primarily specialist institutions and to a larger extent public research entities and colleges. While the strong involvement of colleges was expected from the literature, for the first time we can show the extensive restructuring which took place in the public research entity sector. On the contrary, well known and prestigious university mergers, largely driven by the quest for international visibility, constituted only 10% of the events. Finally, we identified six broad groups of events characterized in terms of two dimensions, i.e. whether the involved organizations are active on the same or different markets and the extent of overlap between subject offerings.

Keywords: mergers, acquisitions, M&A, public research, higher education, public sector research, organizational change.

1 Introduction

The business literature highlighted mergers and acquisitions (M&A) as a major organizational change process of firms (Faulkner, Teerikangas and Joseph 2012). They broadly refer to events in which two or more firms are combined to a new (or redefined as of its perimeter) entity in order to reach goals such as cost reduction, increased visibility and acquiring market shares (Junni and Teerikangas 2019).

In that respect, the literature has documented the frequency and determinants of M&A (Calipha, Tarba and Brock 2010) and has discussed topics such as their impact on firms' strategies and performance (Thanos and Papadakis 2012). The literature also highlighted the complexity of the concept. Beyond the broad distinction between mergers on the one hand and acquisitions on the other hand, different types of transactions are observed depending on dimensions such as the target industry, the characteristics of the buyer, the degree of fit between the involved firms and the strategic goal of the transaction (Teerikangas,

Joseph and Faulkner 2012). Accordingly, various typologies have also been proposed (see Angwin 2012 for a review).

As of the public research sector, a small literature has emerged focusing on mergers in the higher education segment (Pinheiro, Geschwind and Aarrevaara 2016). A number of studies has been published concerning the conditions under which mergers might work (Skodvin 1999), implications for academic synergies (Liu, Patton and Kenney 2018) and reputation of universities (Goedegebuure 1992).

The literature also identified different types of mergers (Goedegebuure 1992). More specifically, mergers were classified according to whether the entities involved are in the same or different sector (for example universities vs. colleges), delivering similar or different products (for example research vs. education) or are in the same or different subject domains.

Most studies however focused on individual cases (e.g. Norgård and Skodvin 2002; Tienari, Aula and Aarrevaara 2016) or on specific countries (Benneworth and de Boer 2016; Harkin and Hazelkorn 2015), while comparative studies analyzing M&A and their characteristics across Europe are still scarce (with the exception of Pruvot, Estermann and Mason 2015). Furthermore, the literature focused on higher education institutions, thereby neglecting the fact that restructuring also took place for other public research entities, largely associated with the devolution of public-sector research from the state (Sanz-Menéndez and Cruz-Castro 2003) and that cross-sectoral M&A, such as the one leading to the creation of the Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT), also took place.

The goal of this paper is to address these limitations by proposing a systematic empirical analysis of M&A in the public research sector, covering higher education institutions (HEIs), public research organizations (PROs) and public administration entities. To this goal, we build on an extensive dataset of M&A made available by the register of public research and higher education organizations (OrgReg) that has been developed within the RISIS2 project (see Lepori in this issue). The database includes nearly 400 M&A events over the period 2000-2016.

As a first step, we provide a systematic overview of M&A, highlighting patterns in terms of the countries in which events took place, frequency over time and the sectors involved. Second, we characterize the landscape of M&A in terms of three dimensions: a) the type of event – mergers vs. acquisition (Eastman and Lang 2001), b) the characteristics of the involved organizations (sector, product, specialization), and c) the regional distribution of M&A.

Third, we review existing typologies and we test the hypothesis that some types of events are more frequent than others (Cai, Pinheiro, Geschwind and Aarrevaara 2016) in order to develop an empirically-grounded categorization of M&A in public research.

While the main contribution of this paper is to provide systematic empirical evidence on the extent and characteristic of M&A in public research, results are also relevant for public policies and for the evaluation of public research. As a matter of fact, M&A in the public sector are closely associated with policy rationales emphasizing competition and international excellence (Sułkowski, Fijałkowska and Dzimińska 2019), as well as the achievement of a critical mass of activities through consolidation processes (Goedegebuure 1992). Yet, evidence on such outcomes is, at best, mixed (Docampo, Egret and Cram 2015; Pinheiro, Geschwind and Aarrevaara 2016) and, mostly, focused on a few highly visible cases of university mergers. A more systematic and representative overview over the whole of public sector, beyond the current focus on higher education, is therefore relevant for understanding the impact of M&A on system's outcomes.

2 Background and motivation

2.1 Definitions

In the business sector, M&A broadly refer to some form of combination or integration between two or more companies in order to generate economic value. In acquisitions, a company acquires the majority of shares and control over a (usually smaller) company, while mergers broadly refer to a combination of equals, in which usually a ‘new’ company is created (Junni and Teerikangas 2019). There is however large variation in the extent of integration ranging from the acquisition of a subsidiary that stays largely independent to wide-ranging integration processes at the organizational level (Angwin 2012).

As an analogue in the public research sector, we define acquisitions as events in which a research or higher education organization acquires control over another research organization; this might imply organizational integration, but also cases in which the acquired organization keeps its functional and legal independence, as well as its own brand (as a ‘part’ of the parent organization). As of mergers, we define them as events in which two or more organizations are integrated into a new organization, as recognized by the state and by the relevant audiences (Sułkowski, Fijałkowska and Dzimińska 2019). In most cases, this involves the creation of a new legal entity and the integration of financial flows through the new organizations. The overall goal is to allow the organization to better address external challenges and opportunities (Harman and Harman 2008).

We focus on the two types of research organizations that comprise the bulk of public research, in order also to analyze for the first time the extent of cross-sector events (see section 3.1 for full details):

- HEIs, delivering tertiary education and, possibly, research, including universities, colleges and various types of other schools, such as arts, music and teacher education schools (Daraio, Bonaccorsi, Geuna, et al 2011).
- PREs, delivering research and, possibly, services and enjoying some autonomy from the state (Bozeman and Bretschneider 1994), including mission-oriented centers, national research centers (such as CNRS or CSIC), research and technology organizations, as well as research units within the public administration (Cruz-Castro, Sanz-Menéndez and Martínez 2012).

The M&A literature has also proposed some dimensions to characterize M&A, as related to differences between the involved organizations in terms of the products they deliver and market positioning. For the purposes of this study, a core distinction is between *horizontal* and *vertical* mergers (Faulkner, Teerikangas and Joseph 2012): in horizontal mergers, the involved organizations produce similar products on the same market and, therefore, the goal is to gain market power either because of increasing visibility or by reducing costs. In public research, large university mergers, such as Aalto in Finland or Bordeaux in France, correspond to this model, where the goal is increasing visibility of the merged university (Docampo, Egret and Cram 2015). In vertical mergers, organizations are involved in different stages of production and, therefore, integration should lead to synergies across the value creation chain. An example in public research is a higher education institution acquiring a research institute in order to develop complementarities between research and education (Sułkowski, Seliga and Woźniak 2020).

2.2 Mergers & acquisitions in public research

The literature on M&A in public research essentially focused on higher education, where such events have been more visible at the political level. They were associated with the expansion of higher education systems, which led to consolidation especially in the professional sector (Kyvik 2004), and to stronger emphasis on competition and international excellence, valuing institutional size more than research intensity (Goedegebuure 1992).

Two waves of mergers have been identified, in the 1980s and 1990s, respectively in the 2000s. Whereas, the mergers attributed to the first wave aimed at *sorting out the system*, demanding for greater efficiency, higher quality and reductions in public budgets (Skodvin 1999), the latter wave was targeted at *raising the bar*, such that mergers increase the international visibility of universities (Hidalgo-Hidalgo and Valera 2016).

Associated to the different purposes, certain determinants of successful mergers have been identified, such as geographical proximity (Skodvin 1999), similar initial reputation (Hidalgo-Hidalgo and Valera 2016), similar historical contexts, as well as the type of key actors (Geschwind et al., 2016) and external stakeholders involved (Stensaker et al., 2016). The success of a merger can be assessed along various dimensions, for instance, organizational consequences, quality and breadth of teaching and research activities (Skodvin, 1999), and national and international excellence (Goedegebuure, 2012).

At the country level, large differences concerning the number and type of M&A events are apparent. In some countries, these events were connected to a *system-wide* restructuring of the public-sector research landscape, induced by public authorities as a response to perceived deficiencies in research systems. Others took place as *incidental* or *voluntary* events, in a primarily local context, initiated by research organizations themselves to improve their strategic position in public research (Goedegebuure 1992).

System-wide restructuring took place, e.g., in *Denmark*, where a comprehensive governmental reform of the public research sector (based on the University Act from 2003 and the Danish Globalisation Strategy from 2006) led to profound changes of the Danish public research landscape, reducing the number of universities from twelve to eight and transferring twelve out of 15 PROs to universities (Aagaard and de Boer 2017). Extensive mergers also affected a number of university colleges. Since 2007, public authorities in *France* induced a general reorganization of higher education, in which some large university mergers, such as the University of Strasbourg and the University of Lorraine, took place, while universities were grouped in communities in 2014 (Pruvot, Estermann and Mason 2015).

Examples for *incidental/voluntary* M&A can be found in *Germany*. For instance, the merger of Karlsruhe Institut für Technologie (KIT) proceeded as part of the “Excellence Initiative”, while the foundation of Leuphana University Lüneburg, was embedded in the “Concept of optimizing HEI structures in Lower Saxony”. Another German example were the mergers of specialized governmental research institutes owned by the Federal Ministry of Food and Agriculture. Although these events were parts of political agendas, M&A have been a rather isolated phenomenon and a large number of events referred to college mergers and regional consolidation (Pruvot, Estermann and Mason 2015).

A *mixture* of incidental and system-wide M&A can be found in *Belgium*. In 2003, five university associations (formal cooperation between one university and at least one university college) were created but they never moved towards institutional integration (Huisman and Mampaey 2016). Subsequently, several local concentration events took place: single mergers between HEIs, colleges and PROs, consolidations on the regional level and of specialized schools and the acquisition of architectural schools by universities.

Other examples for the mixture of system-wide consolidation induced by public authorities and incidental mergers, facilitated by additional public funding, are found in *Finland* (Aarrevaara and Dobson 2016) and in *Norway*, where three phases of mergers can be distinguished (Kyvik and Stensaker 2016): state-initiated forced mergers of regional colleges in the first half of the 1990s, voluntary merger initiatives between 2000 and 2013, and state-initiated forced ‘voluntary’ mergers from 2014 onwards.

2.3 Dimensions of M&A in higher education

A central finding of the literature on M&A in public research is that events are very heterogeneous. While some of the most visible studied cases involve mergers between large universities, many events concerned institutions oriented towards education, such as colleges. Some mergers took place between organizations of similar size, but others represented the acquisition of smaller organizations by large PROs or universities, in which the latter retained its name and branding.

The literature has identified some relevant dimensions for our analysis (see Cai, Pinheiro, Geschwind and Aarrevaara 2016 for a review). First, events can be distinguished based on the sector in which the involved organizations are involved (Harman and Harman 2008). Many earlier events took place among non-university HEIs, whereas later, cross-sectoral events or events within the university sector also took place. Almost all studies of organizational demography analyzed higher education only, while PREs and cross-sectoral events involving HEIs and PREs represent in this respect an unexplored domain.

Second, events can also be distinguished in terms of the products or markets in which the involved organizations are positioned. As of public research, this can be operationalized in terms of education vs. research, as well as of the subject domains of specialization (Lepori, B., Probst and Baschung 2010). In this perspective, Goedegebuure (1992) developed a typology distinguishing between horizontal events (same product and field), diversification events (same product, different field), vertical events (different product, same field) and conglomerate mergers (different product and different field).

Third, Eastman and Lang (2001) distinguished between consolidation events, i.e. events involving organizations of similar size, and acquisition events, in which a smaller institution was absorbed by a larger one, which keeps its identity and visibility.

It has been finally suggested that only some combinations of these characteristics are possible. More precisely, Cai et al. (2016) suggested that most consolidation mergers take place within a single sector, either in the same scientific field (horizontal mergers) or in different fields (diversification mergers). In turn, two types of acquisitions have been proposed: transformative ones between organizations active in the same field, but belonging to different sectors (and offering different products) and semi-autonomous ones between organizations in different sectors and fields, such that integration remains minimal. Yet, we lack a robust empirical basis to test these assumptions derived from individual or country studies.

3 Data and methods

3.1 Data

The analysis is based on a unique and novel set of data provided by the register of public research and higher education organizations (OrgReg; orgreg.joanneum.at). OrgReg is a central facility within the RISIS H2020 project (risis2.eu), which aims at uniquely identifying and tracking “public” and “semi-public” organizations engaged in R&D and higher education over time. OrgReg in principle covers all organizations comprised in higher education, government and private non-profit sectors as defined by the Frascati manual (OECD 2015).

OrgReg has been constructed in successive steps by first identifying all public organizations that have sizeable research output in the Web of Science database (at least 50 publications during the period 2011-2015) or at least 10 participations to European Framework Programs over all years; additionally, all higher education institutions recorded by the European Tertiary Education Register (ETER; Lepori, B., Bonaccorsi, Daraio, et al 2015) have been included, as well as additional relevant public sector research organizations proposed by national experts. Therefore, the coverage of public research and higher education

is very extensive and, at most, only small organizations, contributing little to the public research output, have not been included (see Lepori in this issue for full details). The version of OrgReg used for this paper (as of December 2019) covers 33 European countries (EU-27, Iceland, Israel, Liechtenstein, Norway, Switzerland and UK).

For the purposes of this study, we exclude research hospitals, as the coverage is not currently complete, and private non-profit organizations, due to small numbers, while we group public administration research organizations together with PROs as public research entities (PREs). Our dataset is therefore composed by 3,432 HEIs and 1,315¹ PREs.

3.2 Mergers and acquisitions

OrgReg has been designed to systematically track demographic events, following the EUROSTAT business register definitions (EUROSTAT 2010) and, therefore, it is fully compliant with definitions in the business sector. Demography coverage starts from the year 2000 and is constantly updated.

In general, demographic events involve a break in the continuity of an organization, including birth and death, consolidation of different organizations into a new one or deconsolidation of an organization to multiple children. These have to be distinguished from changes within organizations, such as internal reorganization, name change, change of legal status. Continuity of an organization is defined in terms of activities, human resources and location.

More specifically, the paper analyses two types of demographic events included in OrgReg:

- *Mergers*, i.e. events in which two or more organizations are combined into a new organization, implying the disappearance of the former. The latter is a key criterion to distinguish mergers from the creation of consortia such as the French communities of universities, where members keep their own identity.
- *Acquisitions* (take-overs in the business demography terminology), i.e. events in which an organization is integrated within another organization, which keeps its identity.

To identify mergers, we have first collected information on the foundation year, as organizations founded after the year 2000 are obvious candidates to be the outcome of a merger. Their history has been searched mostly from organizational websites and Wikipedia. Since the OrgReg coverage in the recent years is, by construction, very comprehensive, we also expect that most mergers in public sector from the year 2000 onwards are included.

The identification of acquisitions relied on a combination of methods. First, we looked at the organizations closed after 2000 and included in OrgReg (since they were for example visible in the Web of Science) and checked whether they have been acquired by some other organization. Second, the history of the currently existing organizations was scrutinized from organizational websites and Wikipedia in order to search for acquisitions. Given the timeframe involved, we consider that our sample is very extensive, but we cannot exclude that some small-scale acquisitions have not been identified.

For each event, the corresponding parent organizations were introduced in the register. Organizational information was also completed using information retrieved from the Internet; while this process was sometimes difficult, in most cases enough information could be found. The coding of each event included

¹ This number includes 183 organizations which also award higher education diplomas, mostly research institutes awarding the PhD.

the parent and child organizations, the type of event and the year of occurrence. In this process, very few ambiguous cases were found, mostly referring to cases in which it was unclear whether the event should be considered as an acquisition, since the acquired unit maintained its own visibility. To address these cases, criteria such as organizational control from the parent, branding (for example identification as a member of the parent organization) and control of financial flows were adopted.

3.3 Characterization dimensions

M&A have been characterized according to two dimensions.

a) The *characteristics of the involved organizations* in terms of the sector of activity and the range of research and educational subjects they are covering (Cai, Pinheiro, Geschwind and Aarrevaara 2016).

First, organizations have been classified in three groups in terms of their activities and the markets on which they compete:

- *Colleges*: HEIs, which do not award the PhD. The main institutional mandate is education; their implication in research remains low, with few exceptions (Kyvik and Lepori 2010).
- *Universities*: HEIs awarding the PhD. These institutions have both an educational and research mandate; most of them have a sizeable research activity (Lepori, Benedetto, Geuna and Veglio 2017).
- *PREs*, which do not have an educational mandate, but a research mandate and exceed a minimum volume of research activity.

The information for distinguishing colleges from universities was mainly derived from ETER. In cases where the institution ceased to exist and is not included in ETER, the web archiving service of the digital library “Internet Archive” has been used to collect data from previous versions of the websites, referring to the year closest to the demographic event.

Further, we divided organizations between *specialists* and *generalists*. Generalists cover a broad range of subjects, while specialists are focused on a few of them (Lepori et al., 2010). In practice, this distinction was implemented by considering generalist as organizations active in more than three among ten subject domains of educational statistics (UNESCO-UIS/EUROSTAT 2018). Besides ETER, where data on breakdowns of students by subject are available, information from the websites was the main source of information for PREs.

b) The *regional location* of the event. OrgReg provides geographical information on the main seat of organizations including city and the region, using the NUTS3-2016 classification from EUROSTAT².

In order to address some known issues of the NUTS classification, like regions of very unequal size and different treatment of large cities, we resorted to an adapted regional classification developed by a recent EU project (www.knowmak.eu). More precisely, the classification includes EUROSTAT metropolitan regions (i.e. an aggregation of NUTS3-level regions based on functional urban areas) and NUTS2 regions for the remaining areas.

² See https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/nuts/background_for_detailed_information_on_nuts_classification.

4 Descriptive analysis

4.1 Time and country patterns

Over the period 2000-2016, we have observed 169 mergers and 199 acquisitions distributed over 29 (out of 33)³ countries, in which 897 public organizations were involved, i.e. 19% of the 4,747 organizations included in the dataset. Therefore, a first finding is that M&A are frequent events also in public-sector research and the likelihood for public organizations to be involved is significant (on a rather short time-scale for the public sector).

Further, data show an increasing number of M&A over the considered period (Figure 1), superimposed to yearly peaks associated with structural reforms leading to a large number of M&A in selected countries. In 2007, 15 acquisitions took place in Denmark related to the Danish Globalisation Strategy, while in 2010, the reform of the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences took place, in which several institutes were united. Noticeably, the growth in the number of M&A was also associated with an increasing number of countries in which they took place – from 4 to 6 countries at the beginning of the period to 16 in 2013.

Figure 1. Number of events by year

As shown by Figure 2, in most European countries the number of M&A events was roughly proportional to the size of the public research system, as measured by the number of organizations. Countries with the highest number of HEIs and PREs, like France, Germany, UK and Poland, also had the highest number of events. At the same time, some countries are characterized by a larger number of M&A than it would be expected from the system's size, i.e. Belgium, Hungary, Norway and Denmark; these are the countries in which system-wide restructuring took place over the considered period (see section 2.2). Among the largest European countries, Italy exhibits a low number of M&A; this pattern maybe associated with 1) a highly centralized university-dominated higher education system, with limited opportunities for voluntary concentration processes since universities are largely financed by the government through non-competitive allocation of funds, with low levels of autonomy and responsibilities at the university level (Abramo et al. 2016), and 2) the small number of PREs, given that public research is organized around the National Research Council (CNR). A similar case might be Romania, where the higher education system has been characterized by the homogeneity of universities, limited competition between universities and inefficient

³ The four countries without M&A between 2000 and 2016 are Israel, Lichtenstein, Malta and Slovenia.

non-competitive allocation of public funding; concentration processes are still under negotiation after the Law on Education was adopted in 2011 (Andreescu et al 2015).

Figure 2. M&A by countries and number of HEIs and PREs in OrgReg, 2000-2016

While our database does not allow distinguishing between system-wide and voluntary M&A acquisitions, data are consistent with a pattern in which system-wide restructuring occurred in a few countries (as documented by the literature) superimposed to individual events taking place in many countries with a frequency roughly proportional to the number of organizations in the system (as it would be expected for events driven by local circumstances). Further, our data provide evidence that such individual events were rare in 2000-2005 but have become more frequent and spread over a large number of countries after 2010⁴.

As expected, the outcome of these events was reducing the number of organizations in public research by 451 (from 751 before the events to 300 thereafter). At the same time, the overall number of organizations increased from 3,336 in 2000 to 3,915 in 2016, essentially as an outcome of the foundation of new higher education institutions. Therefore, consolidation went along with the expansion of the higher education system through new foundations. This is consistent with our interpretation that M&A are now mostly incidental and associated with issues of critical mass and market positioning at the level of individual organizations, rather than with the goal of reducing the number of organizations in the whole national system.

4.2 Organizations involved

Overall, the 368 M&A observed have involved 897 organizations in the period 2000-2016. More precisely, 397 organizations were involved in 169 mergers (average 2.3 organizations per merger) leading eventually to 168 newly founded organizations, while 353 organizations were involved in 199 acquisitions of 212 organizations.

⁴ Note that for the first years, the acquisitions of small institutes might not be fully covered in OrgReg. The same pattern is however observed for mergers.

As shown by Table 1, M&A between 2000 and 2016 involved 544 HEIs (60.6%) and 353 PREs (39.4%). When compared with the number of organizations in OrgReg, PREs were significantly more likely to be involved in mergers and acquisitions than HEIs (27% against 16%), the difference being statistically significant ($p < 0.001$).

Therefore, as compared with a literature focused on M&A in the higher education sector, our data show that restructuring in the Public Organizations Sector was more intense than in the HEI sector, at least when considering the number of organizations involved.

Table 1. Types of organizations involved in M&A

Organisation Type	Organizations involved		Organizations in OrgReg		Ratio
Higher Education Institutions	544	60.6%	3,432	72.3%	0.16
Public Research Entities	353	39.4%	1,315	27.7%	0.27
Total	897	100.0%	4,747	100.0%	0.19

A more fine-grained view is provided by Table 2, in which HEIs are further split between universities and colleges, while organizations are also divided between generalists and specialists in terms of their subject coverage.

These data show distinctive patterns. On the one hand, in terms of the organizations involved in M&A, colleges and PREs are much more numerous than universities, while in terms of the organizations existing after the event, the pattern is reversed. This suggests that cross-sectoral events leading to the consolidation of colleges and PREs into universities (either existing or newly created through mergers) is a significant phenomenon.

On the other hand, specialist organizations are much more involved in M&A than generalists; this is expected if the main rationale is to consolidate small organizations to reach critical mass. This pattern is particularly strong for PREs, where many events involved the merging of small institutes the same domain into larger groups. A different pattern is displayed by the university sector, where most events involve generalist organizations, suggesting that a different type of rationale is at work, i.e. achieving international excellence through mergers.

Table 2. Number of organizations involved by specialisation

Type of specialization	Merger		Acquisition	
	before	after	before	after
College generalist	36	23	15	16
College specialist	121	28	97	26
University generalist	40	38	7	57
University specialist	19	13	12	12
Research generalist	3	1		4
Research specialist	178	65	81	26
Total	397	168	212	141

4.3 Regional distribution

As of the regional distribution of events, the M&A literature suggests two patterns: on the one hand, large cities host more organizations and more potential candidates for M&A, since also they are characterized by a larger variety of research and higher education organizations, including many specialized ones. On the other hand, in non-metropolitan regions, issues of consolidation of public research are likely to be more relevant, given the smaller economic and demographic potential. These reflections suggest systematic differences in the extent and types of M&A between metropolitan and non-metropolitan regions.

In that respect, our data provide mixed evidence (Table 3). Indeed, a larger share of metropolitan regions was involved in M&A, i.e. 44% against 33% for non-metropolitan regions and most events took place in metropolitan regions; yet, taking into account that, on the average, a metropolitan region hosts three times more public research entities and higher education institutions than a non-metropolitan region, the difference is rather small. The likelihood for an organization of being involved in M&A is the same in metropolitan (20%) and in non-metropolitan regions (17%), despite the fact that in the former there would be more potential candidates for M&A.

Table 3. Regional distribution of M&A

	METRO		non METRO	
	n	%	n	%
Regions total	275	53%	248	47%
Regions hosting HEIs & PREs	269	54%	226	46%
Regions with M&A	118	61%	76	39%
M&A	374	74%	133	26%
HEIs & PREs in regions	3,524	76%	1,141	24%
HEIs & PREs involved in M&A	699	78%	198	22%
Share of regions with M&A	0.44		0.33	
Average number of M&A per region	3.17		1.75	
Average number of organizations per region	13.00		5.03	
Likelihood for org. to be involved in M&A	0.20		0.17	

Note: Events are assigned to regions based on the location of the involved organizations. There is double counting since a small number of events takes place across metropolitan and non-metropolitan regions. 82 organizations could not be assigned to regions due to lacking NUTS code.

The map displayed in Figure 3 highlights the number of events in which each European region was involved between 2000 and 2016 based on the location of the involved organizations (before and after the event). The map confirms insights from Table 3 that M&A have been widely spread in European regions: the 368 events observed have involved organizations in nearly 200 European regions, while only 17 regions had more than 5 events. The top-regions by number of events include Paris and London, due to their size, but also some smaller regions, which were characterized by structural events either at national level (Copenhagen, Oslo) or specific to the PRE sector (Academy of Sciences in Budapest and Sofia, TECNALIA in Bilbao). Moreover, the map shows a general North-South divide; in countries like Portugal, Italy and Spain, only the large capital regions had such events, while in the Northern and central part of Europe events occurred in most regions.

Figure 3: Regional distribution of demographic events: Number of M&A per region

These results are consistent with the previous analysis suggesting two groups of events, i.e. structural M&A concentrated in single countries and/or capital cities hosting a large number of PREs, superimposed to diffused M&A widely distributed geographically. By providing detailed data on the characteristics and location of organizations involved, OrgReg would allow for a fine-grained analysis of the regional structure of M&A in public research and allow answering questions such as whether characteristics of M&A and of the involved organizations differ by region, the impact of regional characteristics such as population or wealth and the importance of the geographical proximity between organizations involved in M&A events.

5 Characterizing M&A in the public sector

To move towards a characterization of M&A in public research, Figure 4 displays flow diagrams between organizations before and after the event, based on the dimensions introduced in section 3.3, i.e. the distinction between universities, colleges and PREs, as well as between generalist and specialist organizations.

This analysis highlights that some combinations are more frequent than others. As of mergers, the most frequent events are those taking place within a single sector (colleges, universities, PREs), while most acquisitions took place across sectors and, specifically, with universities acquiring colleges and PREs. Moreover, specialist organizations are involved to a larger extent than generalists in M&A, and we observed a sizeable number of cases where specialists have been merged into (or acquired by) generalists.

Figure 4. M&A by specialisation of organizations before and after the events (left: mergers; right: acquisitions)

Note: Nodes represent organizations involved, either as predecessors (parents) or as successors (children). The size of the nodes is proportional to the number of organizations. Directed links point towards the resulting organization after mergers or acquisitions. Link size indicates the number of mergers and acquisitions between these types of organizations.

This analysis allows identifying six groups including about 84% of the events in our database (Table 4).

The first group are events in which specialist PREs have been merged (66 events) or acquired by a larger PRE in the same sector (37 events). Examples are the consolidation of research institutes of the Academy of Sciences in Eastern European Countries (Bulgaria, Hungary, Poland) and the creation of the Max Rubner Institute, which united governmental research organizations in the field of nutrition all over Germany. Few cases involved the consolidation into large generalist PREs such as the Leibniz Institute or the Austrian Research Centers. These events are often associated with the transformation of former research units within the public administration in more autonomous research organizations, which also required consolidating small research unit in neighboring domains into a larger organization (Cruz-Castro, Sanz-Menéndez and Martínez 2012).

A similar process has taken place in the non-university sector, where many college specialists merged (28 events) or were acquired by other college specialists (27 events), which affected especially specialized schools in France as well as colleges in Germany, Croatia, Hungary, Poland and Sweden (group 2). A variant involved the creation of college generalists through merger (23 events) or acquisition (20 events) of college specialists, a common pattern in the Netherlands, but also in Germany, France, Hungary and Poland. Examples are the merger of the two specialized Fachhochschulen in Mannheim to the Fachhochschule Mannheim or the acquisition of teacher training colleges by generalist colleges in Switzerland (group 3).

In these events, the involved organizations are active on the same market, i.e. professional education, and consolidation allows creating larger educational providers with a broader range of offerings. However, in group 2 we expect more overlap between educational offerings, since colleges are active in the same subject domain. Unlike the wave of consolidation in the college sector in the 1990s, which was largely driven by the state and affected whole national systems (Kyvik 2008), during the considered period these events were largely individual and spread over many years and a large number of countries.

On the contrary, events in the university sector mostly affected generalist universities (group 4; 34 events). These mergers and acquisitions were mostly implemented to increase excellence, visibility and competitiveness in the higher education or research market. Most prominent examples are University of Manchester (2004), Aalto University (2010) and the French universities of Strasbourg (2009), Aix-Marseille (2012), Lorraine (2012), Bordeaux (2014), and Montpellier (2015). Although these M&A are comparably few in numbers, they tied up a significant amount of financial and human resources and lasted for several years.

The two last groups involve the acquisition by generalist universities of smaller and more specialized organizations, i.e. specialized educational colleges (group 5; 52 events) or research organizations (group 6; 22 events). An example of the former is the University of Liège taking-over HEC-Liège Business School in 2005, and later I.S.A. Saint-Luc De Wallonie and Institut supérieur d'architecture Lambert Lombard in 2010. In the latter case, smaller research specialists were absorbed by larger University generalists, as in the case of the Roslin Institute, which was acquired by the University of Edinburgh in 2008. From the perspective of the acquiring university, these events might allow strengthening the position in selected markets, such as professional education or applied research, complementarily with existing activities, while, from a public policy perspective, it allows for reducing duplications and streamlining the system's governance.

Table 4. Groups of mergers and acquisitions

Group	Before the event	After the event	Type of Event	Rationale	Examples	N
1 Specialist PRE mergers	Research specialist	Research specialist	Merger or Acquisition	Overcome fragmentation and achieve critical mass; entities remain sometimes independent units at their former locations	Institutes of the Academy of Sciences in Eastern European Countries (BG, CZ, HU, PL); German Institute of Global and Area Studies (DE); National Institute for Aerospace Technology (ES)	103
2 Specialist colleges mergers	College specialists	College specialists	Merger or Acquisition	Consolidation of arts colleges, business schools and technical schools	Stockholm University of Arts (SE), Budapest Business School (HU); Vern University of Applied Sciences, Zagreb (HR), Wrocław School of Banking (PL)	55
3 Generalist colleges mergers	College generalists/specialists	College generalist	Merger or Acquisition	Regional consolidation and broadening the disciplinary scope	Universities of Applied Sciences in BE, DE, FI, NL, PL	43
4 Generalist universities mergers	University generalists/specialists	University generalist	Merger or Acquisition	Increase size, visibility, and competitiveness of metropolitan and regional universities	University of Strasbourg (FR), University of Lorraine (FR), University of Manchester (UK); University of Copenhagen (DK), University of Patras (GR), University College Dublin (IE)	34
5 Acquisitions of colleges by universities	College generalist/specialist	University generalist	Acquisition	Broadening educational offer scope by acquiring colleges, business schools and technical schools	University of Edinburgh (UK), Université de Liège (ULG), Aarhus University (DK), Tallinn University of Technology (EE)	52
6 Acquisitions of PREs by universities	Research specialist	University generalist	Acquisition	Increase scientific excellence, entities remain rather independent	Federal Institute of Technology Lausanne (CH), University of Southern Denmark (DK)	22

By relying on concepts introduced in section 2, we classify these groups across two dimensions (Faulkner, Teerikangas and Joseph 2012). First, whether the involved organizations are active on the same (or proximate) markets or on different markets, i.e. the distinction between horizontal or vertical merger. Second, the extent of overlap between activities and products delivered by the involved organizations (Cai, Pinheiro, Geschwind and Aarrevaara 2016). Obviously, these dimensions are not independent, as horizontal events are expected to lead to stronger overlap. At the same time, higher education and research markets are complex and, frequently, nested: on the one hand, some organizations, such as universities, are inherently multiproduct, while others, such as PREs, are specialized in research; on the other hand, the extent of overlap is also influenced by the subject composition of offerings – specialized colleges might offer the same product, but in different subject domains. Hence, we suggest to consider them independently.

Based on these ideas, we suggest to characterize groups of M&A as in Figure 5. Four groups broadly correspond to horizontal mergers involving organizations that offer a similar range of products (general education vs. professional vs. research services). However, on the lower end, specialized PREs are usually active in neighboring, but distinct subjects, therefore overlap in terms of activities is expected to remain limited, while, on the other end, university mergers tend to involve generalist universities with a significant overlap in their offerings. The remaining two groups broadly correspond to vertical events, in which multiproduct organizations (generalist universities) acquire organizations focused on single markets. While acquired PREs are usually very specialized in specific research services and, therefore, the overlap is low, acquired colleges are likely to overlap in terms of subject offerings, therefore suggesting a potential for transformation and integration.

Figure 5. Characterization of groups of M&A

While this characterization should be considered as tentative and significant variance is expected in individual cases, it nevertheless shows some applicability of concepts derived from the business literature and, specifically, the usefulness of characterizing M&A in the public sector in terms of the ‘markets’ or

‘product offerings’ of the involved organizations. At the same time, it displays the importance of taking into account the multidimensionality of such products and, specifically, the distinction between products (education vs. research) and the subject domains in which they are delivered. Finally, our discussion suggests that such a characterization might be systematically associated with the rationales of the M&A and the extent of transformation of the involved organizations – with lower overlap being associated with semi-autonomous mergers, while high overlap with transformative processes which lead to extensive restructuring. The latter distinction is relevant from a policy and management perspective, as transformative events have a larger potential for synergies, but also entail risks of internal conflicts.

6 Discussion and conclusions

Based on the first comprehensive database of M&A in public-sector research, the goal of this study was to characterize such events alongside three dimensions: a) the type of event, b) the characteristics of the involved organizations, and c) the regional structure of mergers and acquisitions. Furthermore, we characterized M&As in terms of the combinations of organization characteristics of the involved organizations across two dimensions, i.e. the type of product (general education vs. professional education vs. research) and the subject domain (generalist vs. specialist).

First, our data show that M&A represented a major change factor within European public research. Nearly 400 such events occurred in Europe between 2000 and 2016 with an increasing trend over time; M&A involved nearly one-fifth of public-sector research organizations and were geographically distributed – two-fifths of the European regions had at least one event in the considered timeframe.

Data also show that, while in the early years, M&As were limited to a few countries, these processes were more diffused in the second half of the 2000s and, in most European countries, their number was roughly proportional to the size of the national higher education and research system.

While we do not have data on the underlying motivations, our data are broadly consistent with a shift from system-wide processes promoted by the state and concentrated in a few countries and years towards incidental events that are diffused over time and space and triggered by local conditions. In turn, this might be interpreted as the outcome of the shift from tight top-down governance of higher education and research systems by the state to increased autonomy of public research and higher education organizations, reacting individually and strategically to pressures from public authorities, rankings and the local society (Capano 2011).

With respect to the geographical scope of M&As, we identified a stronger presence in Northern and Western Europe. As expected, most events took place in metropolitan regions, but their intensity (as compared with the number of organizations) is similar in metropolitan and non-metropolitan regions.

Second, we identified distinct patterns in terms of the organizations involved and of the types of events. Demographic events concerned primarily specialist organizations and to a larger extent (specialist) PREs and colleges. The strong involvement of colleges was expected from the literature, as these organizations are smaller and more diffused than universities and, hence, issues of consolidation were at the core of the reforms in the college sector in many countries. On the contrary, our data documented for the first time the extensive restructuring which took place in the PRE sector, with nearly one-third of all organizations being involved in M&A over the considered period. We interpret this process as a consequence of the devolution of many research units previously managed by the public administration promoted by New Public Management; units which were previously embedded in distinct administrative contexts, such as ministries or regions had to be consolidated in their new organizational setting (Cruz-Castro and Sanz-Menéndez 2018). At the other end of the spectrum, we identified generalist university mergers as a distinct group of

events, largely driven by the quest for international visibility (Goedegebuure 1992). While more spectacular and potentially impactful, these constituted only 10% of the events in our database.

Finally, we have identified six broad groups of events, which could be characterized in terms of two dimensions, i.e. whether the involved organizations are active on the same or different markets (horizontal vs. vertical events) and the extent of overlap between subject offerings. In this characterization, the two extreme cases are represented by university mergers (horizontal and with large overlap, potentially leading to deep transformation in the involved organizations) and by the acquisition of specialized PREs by generalist universities (vertical and with low overlap, hence with low potential for integration). While still tentative, this analysis therefore suggests the potential value of concepts derived from the business literature on M&A in order to analyze systematically such processes in public research.

As pointed out at several places in the paper, there is a potential for further extending and broadening this analysis. In that respect, the availability of a comprehensive dataset would be an ideal starting point for in-depth studies through the collection of additional data. On the one hand, the longitudinal nature of the dataset would allow, when complemented with quantitative information on resources, underlying rationales, size of organizations, and educational and research output, to provide quantitative results on lasting questions concerning a deeper understanding of determinants and outcomes of demographic events, such as the impact of concentration processes on the research activities and performance of the newly formed organizations and determinants of successful public-sector mergers and acquisitions. On-going work in the RISIS infrastructure project (ris2.eu) to match the OrgReg organizations with data from publication, patents and project databases, as well as to collect basic information on resources and the size of these organizations, is moving in this direction. On the other hand, documentary sources could be collected on the motivations, implementation and outcomes of each individual case; when suitably coded into indicators, such data would allow a more fine-grained characterization of events along the different dimensions of the M&A process. Such information would be highly valuable to inform policy-makers and organizational managers on which practices lead to successful mergers depending on some key characteristics of the context and of the involved organization.

7 Acknowledgements

This work was supported by the European Union through the project *RISIS – Research Infrastructure for Research and Innovation Policy Studies* (Grant agreement no: 313082). The authors want to thank the other members of the RISIS team for useful comments and discussions on the subject.

8 References

- Aagaard, K. & de Boer, H. F. (2017). The Danish UNIK initiative: An NPM-inspired mechanism to steer higher education. In H. Boer, J. F., J. Huisman, M. Seeber, M. Vukasovic, & D. F. Westerheijden (Eds.) *Policy Analysis of Structural Reforms in Higher Education: Processes and Outcomes*. Cham: Springer, 141-159.
- Aarrevaara, T. & Dobson, I. R. (2016). Merger mania? The Finnish higher education experience. In R. Pinheiro, L. Geschwind & T. Aarrevaara (Eds.) *Mergers in Higher Education: The Experience from Northern Europe*. Cham: Springer, 59-72.
- Abramo, G., D'Angelo, C. A., & Rosati, F. (2016). The north-south divide in the Italian higher education system. *Scientometrics*, 109(3), 2093-2117.

- Andreescu, L., Gheorghiu, R., Irimia, A. and Curaj, A. (2015). Mergers and Classifications in Romania: Opportunities and Obstacles. In A. Curaj, L. Georghiu, J. Cassingena Harper, & E. Egron-Polak (Eds.), *Mergers and Alliances in Higher Education: International Practice and Emerging Opportunities*. Heidelberg: Springer, 33-55.
- Angwin, D. (2012). Merger and acquisition typologies: A review. In D. Faulkner, S. Teerikangas & R. J. Joseph (Eds.) *The Handbook of Mergers and Acquisitions* Oxford: Oxford University Press, 40-70.
- Benneworth, P. S. & de Boer (2016). *United Kingdom, higher education mergers in Wales*. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union.
- Bozeman, B. & Bretschneider, S. (1994). The “publicness puzzle” in organization theory: A test of alternative explanations of differences between public and private organizations. *Journal of Public Administration Research and Theory*, 4(2), 197-224.
- Cai, Y., Pinheiro, R., Geschwind, L. & Aarrevaara, T. (2016). Towards a novel conceptual framework for understanding mergers in higher education. *European Journal of Higher Education*, 6(1), 7-24.
- Calipha, R., Tarba, S. & Brock, D. (2010). Mergers and acquisitions: a review of phases, motives, and success factors. *Advances in Mergers and Acquisitions*, 9(1), 1-24.
- Capano, G. (2011). Government continues to do its job. A comparative study of governance shifts in the Higher Education Sector. *Public Administration*, 89(4), 1622-1642.
- Cruz-Castro, L. & Sanz-Menéndez, L. (2018). Autonomy and authority in public research organisations: Structure and Funding Factors. *Minerva*, 56(2), 135-160.
- Cruz-Castro, L., Sanz-Menéndez, L. & Martínez, C. (2012). Research centers in transition: patterns of convergence and diversity. *The Journal of Technology Transfer*, 37(1), 18-42.
- Daraio, C., Bonaccorsi, A., Geuna, A., Lepori, B., Bach, L., Bogetoft, P., Cardoso, M. F., Castro-Martinez, E., Crespi, G. & De Lucio, I. F. (2011). The European university landscape: A micro characterization based on evidence from the Aquameth project. *Research Policy*, 40(1), 148-164.
- Docampo, D., Egret, D. & Cram, L. (2015). The effect of university mergers on the Shanghai ranking. *Scientometrics*, 104(1), 175-191.
- Eastman, J. & Lang, D. (2001). *Mergers in higher education: Lessons from theory and experience*. Toronto: University of Toronto Press.
- EUROSTAT (2010). *Business Registers. Recommendation manual* Luxembourg: EUROSTAT.
- Faulkner, D., Teerikangas, S. & Joseph, R. J. (2012). *The handbook of mergers and acquisitions*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Geschwind, L., Pinheiro, R., & Aarrevaara, T. (2016). The Many Guises of Nordic Higher Education Mergers. In Pinheiro, R., Geschwind, L. and Aarrevaara, T. (Eds), *Mergers in Higher Education: The Experience from Northern Europe*. Cham: Springer, 227-236.

- Goedegebuure, L. (1992). *Mergers in higher Education: a comparative perspective*. Utrecht: Lemma.
- Goedegebuure, L. (2012). *Mergers and More: The changing tertiary education landscape in the 21st century*. HEIK Working paper 2012/01.
- Harkin, S. & Hazelkorn, E. (2015). Restructuring Irish Higher Education through Collaboration and Merger. In A. Curaj, L. Georghiou, J. C. Harper, R. Pricopie, & E. Egron-Pollak (Eds.) *Mergers and alliances in higher education*. Heidelberg: Springer, 105-121.
- Harman, G. & Harman, K. (2008). Strategic mergers of strong institutions to enhance competitive advantage. *Higher Education Policy*, 21(1), 99-121.
- Hidalgo-Hidalgo, M. & Valera, G. (2016). University merging process: a guideline proposal for excellence-enhancing. *The BE Journal of Economic Analysis & Policy*, 16(3), 1359-1386.
- Huisman, J. & Mampaey (2016). *Flanders—Introducing associations in Flemish higher education*. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union.
- Junni, P. & Teerikangas, S. (2019). Mergers and acquisitions. In J. Hearn & D. Collinson (Eds.) *Oxford Research Encyclopedia of Business and Management* Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Kyvik, S. (2008). The non-university higher education sector in Norway. In J. Taylor, J. Brites Ferreira, M. de Lourdes Machado & R. Santiago (Eds.) *Non-university higher education in Europe*. Dordrecht: Springer, 165-185.
- Kyvik, S. (2004). Structural changes in higher education systems in Western Europe. *Higher Education in Europe*, 29(3), 393-409.
- Kyvik, S. & Lepori, B. (2010). *Research in the non-university higher education sector in Europe* Dordrecht: Springer.
- Kyvik, S. & Stensaker, B. (2016). Mergers in Norwegian higher education. In Rómulo Pinheiro, Lars Geschwind & Timo Aarrevaara (Eds.) *Mergers in Higher Education: The Experience from Northern Europe*. Cham: Springer, 29-42.
- Lepori, B., Bonaccorsi, A., Daraio, A., Daraio, C., Gunnes, H., Hovdhaugen, E., Ploder, M., Scannapieco, M. & Wagner-Schuster, D. (2015). *ETER project. Technical report on the data collection* Brussels: European Commission.
- Lepori, B., Probst, C. & Baschung, L. (2010). Patterns of subject mix of higher education institutions: a first empirical analysis from the AQUAMETH database. *Minerva*, 48(1), 73-99.
- Lepori, B., Geuna, A. & Veglio, V. (2017). *A typology of European universities. Differentiation and resource distribution* Brighton: University of Sussex, SPRU Working Paper Series.
- Liu, Q., Patton, D. & Kenney, M. (2018). Do university mergers create academic synergy? Evidence from China and the Nordic Countries. *Research Policy*, 47(1), 98-107.

Norgård, J. D. & Skodvin, O. (2002). The importance of geography and culture in mergers: A Norwegian institutional case study. *Higher Education*, 44(1), 73-90.

OECD (2015). *Frascati Manual 2015. Guidelines for collecting and reporting data on research and experimental development* Paris: OECD.

Pinheiro, R., Geschwind, L. & Aarrevaara, T. (2016). Mergers in higher education. *European Journal of Higher Education*, 6(1), 2-6.

Pruvot, E. B., Estermann, T. & Mason, P. (2015). *DEFINE thematic report: University mergers in Europe*. Brussels: European University Association.

Sanz-Menéndez, L. & Cruz-Castro, L. (2003). Coping with environmental pressures: public research organisations responses to funding crises. *Research Policy*, 32(8), 1293-1308.

Skodvin, O. (1999). Mergers in higher education – success or failure? *Tertiary Education & Management*, 5(1), 65-80.

Stensaker, B., Persson, M., and Pinheiro, R. (2016). When Mergers Fail: A Case Study on the Critical Role of External Stakeholders in Merger Initiatives. *European Journal of Higher Education*, 6(1), 56-70.

Sułkowski, Ł., Fijałkowska, J. & Dzimińska, M. (2019). Mergers in higher education institutions: A proposal of a novel conceptual model. *Managerial Finance*, 45(10/11), 1469-1487.

Sułkowski, Ł., Seliga R. & Woźniak, A. (2020). From coepetition by cooperation to consolidation. contemporary challenges of university mergers and acquisitions. In A. Zakrzewska-Bielawska & I. Staniec (Eds.) *Contemporary Challenges in Cooperation and Coepetition in the Age of Industry 4.0*. Dordrecht: Springer, 175-190.

Teerikangas, S., Joseph, R. & Faulkner, D. (2012). Mergers & acquisitions: A synthesis. In D. Faulkner, S. Teerikangas & R. Joseph (Eds.) *The Handbook of Mergers and Acquisitions*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 661-687.

Thanos, I. C. & Papadakis, V. M. (2012). Unbundling acquisition performance: How do they perform and how can this be measured? In D. Faulkner, S. Teerikangas & R. J. Joseph (Eds.) *Handbook of mergers and acquisitions*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 148-170.

Tienari, J., Aula, H. & Aarrevaara, T. (2016). Built to be excellent? The Aalto University merger in Finland. *European Journal of Higher Education*, 6(1), 25-40.

UNESCO-UIS/OECD/EUROSTAT (2018) *UOE data collection on education systems. Volume 1. Manual. Concepts, definitions, classifications*. Montreal, Paris, Luxembourg.